

User Manual

1 Data Description

1.1 Training data

The training data should include the following feature variables and target variables, formatted as an Excel spreadsheet.

1.2 Data for prediciton

The prediction data only needs to include the following feature variables, formatted as an Excel spreadsheet.

1.3 Detailed description

Feature variables:

- `disp_flow`: Dispersed phase flow rate ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$)
- `cont_flow`: Continuous phase flow rate (mL/h)
- `interfacial_tension`: Interfacial tension between dispersed and continuous phases (N/m)
- `disp_viscosity`: Dispersed phase viscosity ($\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$)
- `cont_viscosity`: Continuous phase viscosity ($\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$)
- `disp_density`: Dispersed phase density (kg/m^3)
- `cont_density`: Continuous phase density (kg/m^3)
- `inner`: Inner diameter of the needle (mm)
- `outer`: Outer diameter of the needle (mm)
- `channel`: Equivalent diameter of the microchannel (mm)

Target variables:

- `diameter` : Droplet diameter (mm)

2 Code Usage Instructions

This folder contains two code files (with the `.py` extension) and two trained model files (Attention Based DNN model with the `.h5` extension and Random Forest model with the `.pkl` extension). Both code files include the complete processes for model training, parameter optimization, invocation, and training with new datasets. The following example uses the Attention Based DNN code (`attention_based_DNN.py`); the same applies to the Random Forest.

2.1 Parameter instructions

This section defines the paths for the training and validation data, feature variables, and target variables. These paths and variables will be used for model training and evaluation. It also defines the path of the trained model that can be used directly or for further training.

```
data_path = 'data.xlsx' # Path to training data, should include feature variables and target variables

validation_path = 'validation.xlsx' # Path to validation data, should include feature variables for model
prediction

new_training_path = 'new_training_data.xlsx' # Path to new dataset, should include feature variables and
target variables

model_path = 'model-attention based DNN.h5' # Path to the trained attention based DNN model

features = ['disp_flow', 'cont_flow', 'interfacial_tension', 'disp_viscosity', 'cont_viscosity', 'disp_density',
'cont_density', 'inner', 'outer', 'channel'] # Feature variable settings

target_var = ['diameter'] # Target variable settings

out_path = 'out_path' # Path to save results
```

2.2 Model Structure Optimization

This function optimizes the neural network structure by testing different numbers of hidden layers and neurons to find the optimal structure. Example usage:

```
data_path = 'data.xlsx'

target_var = ['diameter']

features = ['disp_flow', 'cont_flow', 'interfacial_tension', 'disp_viscosity', 'cont_viscosity', 'disp_density',
'cont_density', 'inner', 'outer', 'channel']

out_path = 'Structure_optimization'

Structure_optimization(data_path, target_var, features, out_path)
```

2.3 Model parameters optimization

This function optimizes the neural network parameters by testing different numbers of hidden layers and neurons to find the optimal parameters. Example usage:

```
data_path = 'data.xlsx'

target_var = ['diameter']

features = ['disp_flow', 'cont_flow', 'interfacial_tension', 'disp_viscosity', 'cont_viscosity', 'disp_density',
'cont_density', 'inner', 'outer', 'channel']

out_path = 'Hyper_parameter_tunning'
```

```
Hyper_parameter_tunning(data_path, target_var, features, out_path)
```

2.4 Training data optimization

This function optimizes the dataset by filtering and retraining the data to improve the model's prediction accuracy. Example usage:

```
data_path = 'data.xlsx'

target_var = ['diameter']

features = ['disp_flow', 'cont_flow', 'interfacial_tension', 'disp_viscosity', 'cont_viscosity', 'disp_density',
'cont_density', 'inner', 'outer', 'channel']

out_path = 'Rank_data'

Rank_data(data_path, target_var, features, out_path)

Rank_train(data_path, target_var, features)
```

2.5 Directly use the trained model

This function loads the trained model and evaluates it using the validation data, outputting the model's prediction results. Example usage:

```
data_path = 'data.xlsx' # Path to the training data used in this model, should include feature variables and
target variables

validation_path = 'validation.xlsx' # Path to the validation data, should include feature variables

model_path = 'model-attention based DNN.h5' # Path to the trained attention based DNN model

features = ['disp_flow', 'cont_flow', 'interfacial_tension', 'disp_viscosity', 'cont_viscosity', 'disp_density',
'cont_density', 'inner', 'outer', 'channel'] # Feature variable settings

target_var = ['diameter'] # Target variable settings

Validation_results(data_path, validation_path, target_var, features, model_path)
```

2.6. Transfer learning

This function adds new training data to do retraining and transfer learning to further improve the model's universality. Example usage:

```
data_path = 'data.xlsx'

new_training_path = 'new_training_data.xlsx'

model_path = 'model-attention based DNN.h5'

features = ['disp_flow', 'cont_flow', 'interfacial_tension', 'disp_viscosity', 'cont_viscosity', 'disp_density',
'cont_density', 'inner', 'outer', 'channel']

target_var = ['diameter']
```

```
new_training(data_path, new_training_path, target_var, features, model_path)
```

3 Requirements

This section lists the Python environment dependencies required for executing data science, machine learning, and deep learning projects. These libraries and tools support data processing, analysis, model training, and result visualization.

3.1 Basic data processing

numpy==1.23.0: For efficient numerical computations, forming the foundation of data processing.

pandas==2.0.0: Provides powerful data structures for data analysis and processing.

scipy==1.10.1: Offers algorithms for mathematics, science, and engineering.

3.2 Machine learning

tensorflow==2.12.0: For building and training complex machine learning models.

keras==2.12.0: For building and training complex machine learning models.

scikit-learn==1.3.2: For data mining and data analysis.

3.3. Image processing and data visualization

matplotlib==3.7.1: Tools for charting and visualization.

opencv-python==4.8.1.78: Computer vision library for processing image and video data.

3.4 Other libraries

In addition to the specialized data processing, machine learning, and image processing libraries mentioned above, our Python environment includes a range of supporting libraries to enhance functionality and ensure stability and efficiency. The libraries and their respective versions included in this environment are listed as follows:

altgraph==0.17.3

anyio==3.6.2

argon2-ffi==21.3.0

argon2-ffi-bindings==21.2.0

arrow==1.2.3

art==6.0

asttokens==2.2.1

astunparse==1.6.3

attrs==23.1.0

backcall==0.2.0

beautifulsoup4==4.12.2

bleach==6.0.0

branca==0.6.0

cachetools==5.3.0

certifi==2022.12.7

cffi==1.15.1

charset-normalizer==3.1.0

colorama==0.4.6

colour==0.1.5

comm==0.1.3

contourpy==1.0.7

cycler==0.11.0

deap==1.3.3

debugpy==1.6.7

decorator==5.1.1

deepctr==0.9.3

defusedxml==0.7.1

dill==0.3.6

et-xmlfile==1.1.0

executing==1.2.0

fastjsonschema==2.16.3

filelock==3.11.0

flatbuffers==23.3.3

folium==0.14.0

fonttools==4.39.3

fqdn==1.5.1

future==0.18.3

gast==0.4.0

google-auth==2.17.1
google-auth-oauthlib==1.0.0
google-pasta==0.2.0
graphviz==0.20.1
grpcio==1.53.0
h5py==2.10.0
hmmlearn==0.3.0
idna==3.4
importlib-metadata==6.1.0
importlib-resources==5.12.0
install==1.3.5
ipykernel==6.23.1
ipython==8.12.2
ipython-genutils==0.2.0
ipywidgets==8.0.6
iso8601==2.0.0
isoduration==20.11.0
jax==0.4.8
jedi==0.18.2
Jinja2==3.1.2
joblib==1.2.0
jsonpath==0.82
jsonpointer==2.3
jsonschema==4.17.3
jupyter==1.0.0
jupyter-console==6.6.3
jupyter-events==0.6.3
jupyter_client==8.2.0
jupyter_core==5.3.0
jupyter_server==2.5.0

jupyter_server_terminals==0.4.4

jupyterlab-pygments==0.2.2

jupyterlab-widgets==3.0.7

keras==2.12.0

kiwisolver==1.4.4

libclang==16.0.0

lxml==4.9.2

Markdown==3.4.3

MarkupSafe==2.1.2

matplotlib==3.7.1

matplotlib-inline==0.1.6

mistune==2.0.5

ml-dtypes==0.0.4

mlxtend==0.22.0

mpmath==1.3.0

multiprocess==0.70.14

nbclassic==1.0.0

nbclient==0.7.4

nbconvert==7.4.0

nbformat==5.8.0

nest-asyncio==1.5.6

networkx==3.1

notebook==6.5.4

notebook_shim==0.2.3

numpy==1.23.0

oauthlib==3.2.2

opencv-python==4.8.1.78

openpyxl==3.1.2

opt-einsum==3.3.0

packaging==23.0

pandas==2.0.0

pandocfilters==1.5.0

parso==0.8.3

patsy==0.5.3

pefile==2023.2.7

pgmpy==0.1.22

pickleshare==0.7.5

Pillow==9.5.0

pkgutil_resolve_name==1.3.10

platformdirs==3.5.1

playsound==1.3.0

prettytable==3.7.0

prometheus-client==0.16.0

prompt-toolkit==3.0.38

protobuf==4.22.1

psutil==5.9.5

pure-eval==0.2.2

pyasn1==0.4.8

pyasn1-modules==0.2.8

pycm==4.0

pycparser==2.21

pyecharts==2.0.3

pygame==2.5.2

Pygments==2.15.1

pyinstaller==5.9.0

pyinstaller-hooks-contrib==2023.2

pyparsing==3.0.9

pyrsistent==0.19.3

pysam-win==0.5.11

pyserial==3.5

PySide2==5.15.2.1

python-dateutil==2.8.2

python-json-logger==2.0.7

pytz==2023.3

pywin32==306

pywin32-ctypes==0.2.0

pywinpty==2.0.10

PyYAML==6.0

pyzmq==25.0.2

qtconsole==5.4.3

QtPy==2.3.1

requests==2.28.2

requests-oauthlib==1.3.1

rfc3339-validator==0.1.4

rfc3986-validator==0.1.1

rsa==4.9

scikit-learn==1.2.2

scipy==1.10.1

seaborn==0.12.2

Send2Trash==1.8.2

serial==0.0.97

shiboken2==5.15.2.1

simplejson==3.19.1

six==1.16.0

sklearn-genetic==0.5.1

sniffio==1.3.0

soupsieve==2.4.1

stack-data==0.6.2

statsmodels==0.13.5

sympy==1.11.1

tensorboard==2.12.1

tensorboard-data-server==0.7.0

tensorboard-plugin-wit==1.8.1

tensorflow==2.12.0

tensorflow-estimator==2.12.0

tensorflow-intel==2.12.0

tensorflow-io-gcs-filesystem==0.31.0

termcolor==2.2.0

terminado==0.17.1

threadpoolctl==3.1.0

tinycss2==1.2.1

tkmacosx==1.0.5

tornado==6.3.2

tqdm==4.65.0

traitlets==5.9.0

typing_extensions==4.5.0

tzdata==2023.3

uri-template==1.2.0

urllib3==1.26.15

wcwidth==0.2.6

webcolors==1.13

webencodings==0.5.1

websocket-client==1.5.1

Werkzeug==2.2.3

widetsnbextension==4.0.7

wrapt==1.14.1

zipp==3.15.0